

RELEVANCE AND IMPORTANCE OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN THE STATE CIVIL SERVICE

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Abstract: In this article, state civil servants as human resources should regularly develop their knowledge, qualifications and skills for the effective functioning of state bodies and organizations, to exercise their powers, as well as the content of the adopted regulatory legal documents on the development of professional competences of state civil servants. - its essence is explained in detail.

In today's state civil service, human resources are leaders and employees working in the management apparatus of organizations and agencies related to the state civil service system, in a word, state civil servants. State civil service is a type of state service, which represents the paid professional activity of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure the implementation of the powers of state bodies in the positions of state civil service. For the effective functioning of the state civil service, it directly depends on the people who put it into action. Therefore, it is not an exaggeration to say that the efficiency of the state civil service comes from the potential of state civil servants.

As the Head of our state noted, "In today's rapidly changing world, new problems and questions arise every day. Therefore, every specialist should work on himself, acquire new knowledge."

When we talk about the issue of competence in the public civil service, we understand the knowledge, skills, abilities of civil servants in their field and the ability to put it into practice.

How to increase the competence of civil servants? In order to answer this question, let's analyze the regulatory documents adopted in this field and the work being carried out.

Analyzing one by one the legal documents adopted in recent years in the direction of human resources development in the state civil service, we can see that there are sufficient legal bases in this regard. In particular, if we take the Labor Code adopted in 1995 as the first basis, we can see that in its article 16, there is a norm related to the basic labor rights of the employee related to his professional training, retraining and improvement of skills. In addition, in Article 13 of the new version of the Law "On Education" adopted in 2020, there is a

norm on "Retraining of personnel and improvement of their qualifications".¹ In addition, in Article 13 of the new version of the Law "On Education" adopted in 2020 ² The norm on "Retraining of personnel and improvement of their qualifications" is presented. It is the norm on improving the qualifications of state civil servants based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 3, 2019 "On measures to fundamentally improve the personnel policy and state civil service system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-5843, paragraph 10, part 1, "State bodies and "It is stipulated that it is necessary to ensure that state civil servants of organizations pass short-term (30-60 hours) training courses every year, separated from production."

The first goal of the Decree No. 60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 29, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" is the 10th goal "State civil service" in the direction of "Elevation of human dignity and further development of a free civil society". organization of the system based on modern standards" is defined. It defines the task of improving the system of raising the level of professional training, material and social security of civil servants.

In addition, Decree No. PF-269 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2022 "On measures to implement the administrative reforms of New Uzbekistan" and "On measures to effectively organize the activities of the executive authorities of the republic within the framework of the administrative reforms of New Uzbekistan" In Decision No. 447³ the executive authorities of the republic are assigned the task of filling the relevant structures with qualified personnel, developing and implementing systematic measures aimed at continuous improvement of their knowledge and skills.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Civil Service" of December 8, 2022 was the most important of the adopted legal frameworks. Several articles of this law contain norms for the development of professional competencies of state civil servants, including professional development.

In particular, in Article 4 of the Law ⁴ it is stated that the professional competence of a civil servant is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the proper implementation of the powers of the state body.

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Меҳнат кодекси, 21.12.1995 й., <https://lex.uz/docs/142859?ONDATE=01.04.1996%2000>

² Ўзбекистон Республикасининг "Таълим тўғрисида"ги қонуни, 24.09.2020 й., Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 24.09.2020 й., 03/20/637/1313-сон; Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 21.04.2021 й., 03/21/683/0375-сон, 12.10.2021 й., 03/21/721/0952-сон

³ Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 24.12.2022 й., 07/22/447/1118-сон

⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг "Давлат фуқаролик хизмати тўғрисида"ги Қонуни, 08.08.2022 й., Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 09.08.2022 й., 03/22/788/0723-сон

According to the above legislation, we can see that there are legal bases aimed at developing the professional competencies of civil servants. However, as another legal basis, it is required to develop a unified procedure and mechanism for the systematic development of professional competencies of state civil servants in the Republic.

In this procedure, first of all, what competencies a civil servant of the state should have, how these competencies are formed, the processes of retraining and advanced training of the civil servant, as well as the requirements for educational institutions should be reflected.

As an example, at the initiative of the State Service Development Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a total of 5,260 state civil servants in the region were trained in traditional and remote form during the year 2022 alone. This is 60 percent of the total state civil servants in the region. In particular, over the past year, 512 middle and lower level managers have developed their knowledge, skills and abilities in the Samarkand regional branch of the State Administration Academy under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This indicator is 56% of the total number of leaders in the region.

These training courses were financed from the state budget. If we analyze these leaders according to their positions, at the regional level, 5 of them are department heads, 24 are deputy department heads, 105 are department heads and branch managers, 45 are personnel service managers of departments, 297 department heads and managers are at the district (city) level. 36 deputy heads of departments were trained.

Comparing these indicators with 2021, we can see that in 2021, a total of 194 managers were trained, and this indicator increased by 62% in 2022.

Indicators of training of managerial personnel (2022)

Indicators of training of leading personnel (2021-2022)

In addition to traditional training courses, 50-hour training courses were organized through the distance training platform of the Main Scientific and Methodological Center (BIMM) starting from 2022 in cooperation with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education at the initiative of the Agency. During 2022, a total of 4,748 state civil servants in the region were trained in these distance training courses. If we analyze them according to their positions, 64 district (city) sector leaders, 72 leaders included in the national personnel reserve, 116 candidates included in the potential personnel reserve (neighborhood mayor's assistants, youth leaders and women's activists), 44 members of the "Leaders of the Future" club, as well as employees of regional offices and district (city) departments of state bodies and organizations, were

trained and received certificates. Today, 83 district and city deputy mayors and 67 state civil servants are improving their skills through the remote platform. In addition, "Political (Enlightenment) training hours" are held for state civil servants on Fridays of the week, in which the most important news that happened in our country and abroad during the week, the summary of the newly adopted regulatory documents, the importance of the reforms implemented in our country will be covered in detail and literature will be recommended for reading during the week. It is possible to follow these training hours at any time through social networks.

It is difficult to say that the opportunities created for the development of human resources are still giving effective results for everyone. The reason is that there is currently no single system that assesses the level of development of the professional competences of all state civil servants and the effective organization of their activities (with the exception of KPI indicators of district (city) sector heads and deputy governors). In addition, public civil servants are also required to have an interest in professional development. For example, every human resource in the public service should be able to use such opportunities, as if a school teacher works on himself and successfully passes the certification, an additional increase is added to his monthly salary. The professional competence of the civil servant is evident in the following cases:

- in complex processes;
- performing unclear tasks;
- using conflicting information;

In addition, today it is necessary to bring the development of the professional competences of state civil servants to a higher level, not in terms of numbers, but also in terms of content, to develop the knowledge and skills necessary for them to perform their duties properly, thus turning the public service into a system that pleases the people.

Civil servant with professional competence:

- he not only improves his skills in training courses, but also consistently enriches his knowledge;
- learns new information;
- deeply understands the requirements of the era;
- seeks new knowledge;
- process them and use them effectively in their practical work.

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